

Bromomethylation of aromatics mediated by low frequency ultrasound

Jitender M. Khurana* and Golak C. Maikap

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

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We report herein bromomethylation of aromatics mediated by low frequency ultrasound to yield bromomethylated aromatic rings which are useful synthetic intermediates.

The increasing importance of ultrasound to catalyse otherwise slow reactions and its usefulness in organic synthesis¹ is receiving considerable attention. Many a two-phase reactions which made the use of phase transfer catalyst indispensable as well as metal-surface reactions proceed smoothly under ultrasonic irradiation². The chloromethylation of aromatic rings is well studied³ though the yields are often variable and invariably other undesired products are also formed. The bromomethylation of aromatic rings has been neglected in spite of the greater synthetic utility of bromomethyl aromatics.

We now report a simple and convenient procedure for the bromomethylation of aromatic rings with paraformaldehyde, 48% aqueous hydrobromic acid and acetic acid and exposing the reaction mixture to ultrasonic waves. The reactions are complete in 2–10 h at ambient temperature. The yields are nearly quantitative and no undesired products are obtained. The results are listed in Table 1. Only monobromomethylated products were obtained in all cases except mesitylene in which bis-bromomethylation competes with monobromomethylation. This could be attributed to the higher reactivity of mesitylene towards electrophiles. The reaction of toluene and ethylbenzene with paraformaldehyde, aqueous HBr and acetic acid gave little or no bromomethylation products without exposure to ultrasound up to 24 h. No bromomethylation was observed in the reaction of nitrobenzene even after prolonged reaction time due to electron-withdrawing nature of the nitro group. The bromomethylations may be proceeding in a way analogous to chloromethylations³.

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded on a Tropical Labequip apparatus and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Hitachi FT-NMR (60 MHz) spectrometer with TMS as internal standard and GC analyses performed on a Shimadzu instrument equipped with a column of 5% SE-30 (3 m) on chromosorb w and flame ionization detector (FID). HPLC analyses were

Table 1. Bromomethylation of aromatics using $(\text{CH}_2\text{O})_n/\text{HBr}/\text{HOAc}$ on ultrasonic irradiation

Substrate (ArH)	ArCH ₂ Br	Reaction time (h)	Yield ^a %
Toluene	4-Methylbenzyl bromide	7	87 (90) ^b
<i>p</i> -Xylene	2,5-Dimethylbenzyl bromide	5	93
Ethylbenzene	4-Ethylbenzyl bromide	7	93
Cumene	4-Isopropylbenzyl bromide	10	75 (80) ^c
<i>p</i> -Cymene	2-Methyl-5-isopropylbenzyl bromide	10	81 (85) ^d
Naphthalene	1-Bromomethylnaphthalene	3	92
2-Methylnaphthalene	1-Bromomethyl-2-methylnaphthalene	4	95
Mesitylene	2,4,6-Trimethylbenzyl bromide	2.5	46 (55) ^e
Nitrobenzene	–	15	<i>f</i>

^aYield in parenthesis is GC yield unless otherwise specified.

^b8% of toluene was also detected by GC in the reaction mixture.

^c12% of cumene was also detected by GC in the reaction mixture.

^d15% of *p*-cymene was also detected by GC in the reaction mixture.

^eYield in parenthesis is HPLC yield; HPLC analyses also showed the presence of bis-bromomethylated product (40%).

^f = Starting material recovered unchanged.

done on a Shimadzu LC-4A instrument with ODS-18 column (150 mm × 4 mm, Zorbax) and UV detector. Ultrasonic cleaning bath Ralsonics R-120 (120 W, 3L) was used. GC/HPLC ratios are reported as nearest whole numbers.

General procedure : A mixture of aromatic compound (0.05 mol), paraformaldehyde (1.5 g, 0.05 mol), 48% aqueous HBr (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (7 ml) was exposed to ultrasound in a ultrasonic cleaning bath. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and GC. The reaction mixture was then poured into water (100 ml) and stirred well for 10 min. The products were extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 15 ml), washed with 5% sodium bi-

carbonate (10 ml) and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . The filtrate was concentrated and the product was obtained by distillation under reduced pressure (runs 1-5), by recrystallisation (runs 6-7) or separation by column chromatography (silica gel 100–200 mesh, eluent : benzene) (run 8). The products were characterized by m.p./b.p. and ^1H nmr spectra.

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References

1. J. J. Mason, "Sonochemistry : The Uses of Ultrasound in Chemistry", Royal Society of Chemistry, London, 1990; J. Lindley and T. J. Mason, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1987, **16**, 275; T. J. Mason and J. P. Lorimer, *Endeavour*, 1989, **13**, 123; J. M. Khurana, P. K. Sahoo and G. C. Maikap, *Synth. Commun.*, 1990, 2267.
2. C. Einhorn, J. Einhorn and J. L. Luche, *Synthesis*, 1989, 787, and references cited therein; J. M. Khurana, P. K. Sahoo, S. S. Titus and G. C. Maikap, *Synth Commun.*, 1990, 1357.
3. R. C. Fuson and C. H. McKeever, *Org. React.*, 1942, **1**, 63, and references cited therein; G. A. Olah and S. H. Yu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 2293; F. Fernandes, G. Gomez, L. Lopez and A. Santos, *Synthesis*, 1988, 802; P. L. Baker and C. Bahia, *Tetrahedron*, 1990, **46**, 2691; P. R. Giles and C. H. Mason, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, 5227; A. G. Shipov, I. A. Savostyanova and Y. I. Bankov, *J. Gen. Chem. (USSR)*, 1989, **59**, 1067; L. P. Turchaninova, A. Korchevin, A. G. Shipov, E. N. Deryagina, Y. A. Bankov and M. G. Voronkov, *J. Gen. Chem. (USSR)*, 1989, **59**, 638.